

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC WORLD VIEW OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article states that one of the most important directions of state policy in the field of public education is the development of the intellectual and creative potential of young people, the creation of the necessary conditions for supporting and encouraging talented children, as well as raising their level of consciousness, arming them with worldly knowledge.*

Keywords: *youth, psychology, social, worldview, personality, development, mental phenomena, intellectual, integration, science, practice, applied, social.*

Introduction. The solution of scientific problems in psychology is related to their effective application in practice. Stress, suicide, communication, determination of professional skills, professional reorientation, psychological prevention, psychological enlightenment, psychological consultation and counseling in all social spheres, psychological services that develop personality and shape creativity and creativity of the population and state bodies are widely studied in science. (neighborhood, school, authority) needs are great.

Teachers are the main part of higher education. Students' arrival, departure, behavior, and what they do in higher education will not be included in the student's daily scenario. Even with enough planning, it might not happen. It is permissible to describe the incident as an example. A teacher comes to class and a student stays late. It comes in the course of the lesson. The teacher asks him why he is late. Then the student says that he is late with his problem. Then the teacher shouts at the student. And the student is depressed. As a result, the student injures himself. In such situations, it is appropriate for the psychologist to monitor the teacher and student, how they enter higher education, their mood, physical and mental state, behavior, behavior, and relationship with others.

Educational psychology is a relatively new field of study. However, throughout history there have been thinkers concerned with teaching and learning processes; and some of his ideas are still relevant today. For example, philosophers in classical antiquity such as Plato and Aristotle studied individual differences in areas such as learning, physical abilities, or the development of psychomotor skills. In addition, they studied the impact of the arts on learning and tried to understand the role that teachers should play and their relationship with students.

One of the most important issues in educational psychology is how individual differences can affect the acquisition of new knowledge. Since the emergence of this field of psychology, many researchers have tried to find which personal factors are the most important to study.

As a result of the population's lack of psychological knowledge in solving social problems, there is an increase in the number of family crises, divorces, and an increase in the number of crimes among the population, especially among women and children. It is important to give a psychological characterization of a person for admission to the service, to conduct forensic psychological examinations and give conclusions, to give conclusions on the distribution of

children to parents as a result of family decisions, at a competent level and based on scientific grounds.

The small number of private psychological service centers, their lack of competence and license for all types of psychological services, cannot satisfy the needs of the population for psychological services in social life. It is urgent to research the problems of developing special ways and creating opportunities for graduates of higher education to effectively apply their theoretical knowledge in professional practice.

The main idea of our research was to select for discussion the actual problems of integration of psychological science with philosophical, socio-economic, natural, concrete sciences and direct their research to the judgment of the researchers, to teach students and experts to think about it. Psychological knowledge is reflected in all fields, production, production management, education, and especially the medical field, together with the science of psychology, are gaining influence. These areas are more effective when conducted based on psychological knowledge [2].

Psychology is used not only in education and medicine, but also in the fields of politics, economy, service, culture and sports. This is increasingly becoming a tradition, increasing the prestige and responsibility of our science in society. The purpose of covering this topic is to study new approaches, laws, regularities, mechanisms, theories to the science of psychology in the current globalization and integration processes.

Our task is to develop the psychological technology of actual general psychological problems and their research, to develop and introduce innovative psychological methods for psychological specialists to acquire knowledge and skills in the national, general theoretical and general practical aspects of modern psychology.

In addition, in the psychology of the 21st century:

study the methodology and phenomenology of integration problems of science and production:

learning to modern analysis of biosphere and mesospheric approaches;

reveal psychological categories and their essence;

issues of introduction to the psychological technology of conducting research on current problems are defined.[1]

The development of interdisciplinarity and integration of disciplines in society is the reason for the increased interest in the problem of personality. It is the cognitive processes of the person that allow to study the individual-psychological characteristics of the psychological states. The application of information on this scientific problem to the educational process helps to consciously control the behavior of a person in all aspects of his development. It also allows processing of research results. As well as studying other sciences, the study of the penetration of psychology into social spheres, combining with other sciences and creating new scientific problems is a new stage in the field of obtaining new scientific information in the field of psychology.

Psychology is closely related to all socio-economic, socio-political spheres of society. Because the human personality is active in every field, it is necessary to organize work effectively in every field, to manage human behavior in different situations, human psychology, psychology of interpersonal relations, to know the behavioral norms of people in different situations, to create technology in accordance with human abilities, and on the other hand it is important to educate

and adapt according to the technological norms of thinking and actions. These require that today's specialists be aware of psychological knowledge.

Since the 90s of the 20th century, this scientific problem has been the focus of the leading scientists of our republic. The representatives of the scientific school created by doctors of psychological sciences, professors E. Goziev, G. Shoumarov, V. Karimova, B. Kadirov reflected the problem of interdisciplinary integration in each of their works.

Psychology of the 21st century is distinguished by its applied character and branches. In the 21st century, the study of the fields in which the science of psychology is rapidly integrated shows the importance and benefits of the science of psychology in society. The integration of psychology is important for human development and health. If we achieve rapid integration of the following fields with the science of psychology:

- pedagogy, education;
- physiology of age periods;
- sociology;
- production;
- engineering, nanotechnologies;
- jurisprudence;
- military field;
- economy;
- medicine;
- the development of management and other areas, the effectiveness of its management will increase [4].

This idea is based on the social needs of the society, and as it was mentioned above, due to the small number of psychological service centers in the republic, state organizations and specialists of higher education institutions provide services to the population in this regard. We focused on determining the place and opportunities of psychology in society by analyzing the psychological essence of all the changes taking place in the life of our society from the point of view of today's integrative level, state and perspective of psychology.

These viewed issues provide a brief summary of psychology's production, social life, and interdisciplinary integration-relationship and its importance. In a certain sense, it gives an idea of the possibilities of psychology as a tool of scientific practice and scientific research. Based on the tasks of the science of psychology, the study of the social-psychological mechanisms of the system of many complex relationships of a person with society has not yet been realized.

The integration of the science of psychology together with all fundamental and applied fields achieves effectiveness in socio-historical and concrete production conditions, brings about qualitative changes in the individual.

According to the modern concept of the science of psychology "The main tasks of interdisciplinary and integration of science with practice:

serving the development of natural sciences; use of the achievements of natural sciences - physics, chemistry, biology to influence human psychology;

effective use of scientific information obtained in the field of specific sciences in the field of psychology;

restoration of connection between social and humanitarian sciences.

The following principles are taken into account when performing practical tasks:

1. Ways to create a balance between a person and his profession. In other words, it is necessary to study the laws of the dynamic system between "Labor subject - professional environment".

2. To study the composition and dynamics of professionally important characteristics of an individual and a person.

3. To study the stability and dynamics of competence, skills and habits in solving professional tasks in optimal and extreme conditions.

4. To study human institutions and motives, to change their composition if necessary.

5. Study of psychological characteristics of a person in the process of social relations.

6. To study and explain the dependence of the factor of labor efficiency and safety on the psychology of the individual.

Integration of psychology and improvement of production efficiency has its own psychological, psychodiagnostic, psychocorrective and prognostic tasks. The science of integrative psychology has a long history and covers a wide range of issues. Its integration with each field has its own rules and features, and requires a consistent study and approach, applied in the process of higher education. The integration of nanotechnologies is considered a close science with engineering psychology and ICT sciences, today the development of science and technology, the creation of technologies has brought great changes to the science of psychology, it has created scientific research requirements for researchers and future specialists-students.

The development of society and changes in production conditions are putting new tasks before the science of psychology. However, the theories created in the history of science have not lost their scientific value, but new technical discoveries and technological innovations are being created based on these laws.

The study of the integration of the science of psychology in the conditions of globalization makes an important contribution to the study of the psychology of a person under the influence of global information.

As we know, globalization consists of two stages:

1. Differentiation.

2. Integration.

The science of psychology was differentiated in the structure of the science of philosophy in the distant past, starting from the VII century BC.

Since the beginning of the 20th century, the science of psychology has experienced integration processes. Psychological knowledge began to be used in all spheres - science, production, social spheres. By the 21st century, the importance of this integration is increasing under the influence of global globalization, development of human thinking and other factors.

Any society looking for high development in the future will pay attention to interdisciplinary integration, integration of science and production, integration of science, education and production, which will lead to effective results. Integrative processes have their own characteristics in psychology. Three main directions of psychological integration can be indicated.

I. Related to the factors of development of psychological knowledge. Based on the concept of Wilhelm Wundt, first of all, it is time to change the perception of the subject of psychology.

In modern psychology, knowledge related to the essence of cognitive psychology - knowledge related to the immanent features of psychological knowledge, along with general psychological knowledge, psychological knowledge related to a special field is important.

II. It is related to the application of psychological knowledge in other disciplines. The success of many sciences is due to the direct connection of theoretical information with practical psychology. This is the result of the social importance of psychology.

III. It is a generalization of the above-mentioned two directions, and it can be called constructive, creative [6].

In order to put research results into practice, it is necessary to create new theoretical foundations that are common to the theoretical concept of various disciplines. Second, there is a need for an adequate method and instrument to ensure successful practical activity. In this regard, it is undoubtedly based on the historical and modern experience of world psychological schools. It should be noted that the importance of V. Wundt's laboratory is recognized in the recognition of psychology as an independent science throughout the world. Laboratory activities revealed a new theoretical concept, method and research instrument. The laboratory has become an international center for training professional psychologists; special monographs and journals began to be published; international congresses on psychology began to be held regularly.

Conclusions and suggestions. The solution to the analyzed problem can be the establishment of scientific laboratories under the universities or in an independent form for students to carry out scientific researches and their implementation, and having mature specialist scientists and technical base of these laboratories. Initially, existing scientific research institutes and higher education institutions in our republic can serve as a foundation for these laboratories.

In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, the presence of independent thinking young people is the need of the times, because only people with a personal worldview will be able to achieve success that ensures the development of society. One of the main factors of the policy carried out in the republic is the development and training of talented individuals with deep thinking, independent outlook.

REFERENCES

1. Action strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. 2017 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. Ismailovich S. A. Socio-Psychological Problems of Educating an Independent-Minded, Creative Person in the Educational Process //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 4-7.
3. Saidov A., Djuraev R. The role of sports in the formation of a mature generation - the formation of a healthy lifestyle // Obshchestvo i innovatsii. - 2021. - T. 2. – no. 2. - S. 203-208.
4. Saidov A. Pedagogical skills: forming a healthy lifestyle among young people as a priority //tsentr nauchnyx publikatsiy (buxdu. en). - 2020. - T. 2. – no. 2.
5. Sharifjon Tolkin Og A. et al. The importance of psychological services in the educational system and teachers activities //models and methods for increasing the efficiency of innovative research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 57-60.
6. Saidov A. Social and psychological issues of raising a healthy and well-rounded person //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – T. 1. – №. Special issue. – C. 262-266.